

APPENDIX A
NOMENCLATURE

The main notations are defined in the following. Other symbols are defined as needed throughout the text.

A. Indices and superscripts

n	Index of buses.
i	Index of PV systems.
s	Index of BES systems.
t	Index of time-periods.
k	Index of scenarios.
$\text{up}(n)$	Upstream bus of bus n .
PF	Power flow.
PV	Photovoltaic system.
BES	Battery energy storage system.
DM	Demand.
SC	Scheduled value.
DP	Deployed magnitude.
net	Net power.
$\uparrow, \downarrow$	Positive and negative flexibilities.
C	Charging.
D	Discharging.

B. Sets

$\mathcal{N}$	Set of buses.
$\mathcal{T}$	Set of time-periods.
$\mathcal{K}$	Set of scenarios.
$\mathcal{I}_n$	Set of PV systems at bus n .
$\mathcal{S}_n$	Set of BES systems at bus n .
$\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R}_+$	Real numbers and real non-negative numbers set.
$\mathcal{D}$	Ambiguity set.
$\Psi(\cdot)$	Set of all possible distributions.

C. Variables

v_{nt}	Voltage square of bus n .
l_{nt}	Square of the current flowing in the central element of line n model.
p_{nt}	Active power flow entering bus n from the bottom.
q_{nt}	Reactive power flow entering bus n from the bottom.
$v_{nt}^{(up)}$	Voltage square of bus “up(n)”.
$p_{nt}^{(up)}$	Active power flow entering bus n from the top.
$q_{nt}^{(up)}$	Reactive power flow entering bus n from the top.
$p_{nt}^{(DM)}$	Active power consumption at bus n .
$q_{nt}^{(DM)}$	Reactive power consumption at bus n .
$p_{it}^{(PV)}$	Active power production of PV system i .
$q_{it}^{(PV)}$	Reactive power production of PV system i .
$p_{st}^{(BES)}$	Active power production of BES system s .
$q_{st}^{(BES)}$	Reactive power production of BES system s .
$p_{nt}^{(net)}$	Net active power injection to bus n .
$q_{nt}^{(net)}$	Net reactive power injection to bus n .
e_{st}	SoC of BES system s .
$p_t^{(SC)}$	Delivered active power at the connection node.
$q_t^{(SC)}$	Delivered reactive power at the connection node.
$r_t^{(p\uparrow)}$	Booked upward active power flexibility.
$r_t^{(p\downarrow)}$	Booked downward active power flexibility.

$r_t^{(q\uparrow)}$	Booked upward reactive power flexibility.
$r_t^{(q\downarrow)}$	Booked downward reactive power flexibility.
$p_t^{(DP)}$	Deployed active power in real-time.
$q_t^{(DP)}$	Deployed reactive power in real-time.

D. Parameters

N	Numbers of buses.
I_n	Numbers of PV systems at bus n .
S_s	Numbers of BES systems at bus n .
T	Numbers of time-periods.
K	Numbers of scenarios.
Z	Numbers of uncertain parameters.
$u_{nn'}$	A binary parameter $u_{nn'}$, in which $u_{nn'} = 1$ if $n' = \text{up}(n)$ and $u_{nn'} = 0$ otherwise.
r_n	Resistance of line n .
x_n	Reactance of line n .
$2b_n$	Shunt impedance of line n .
$1 - \epsilon$	Confidence-level.
δ	Maximum permissible deviation from the deployed active and reactive power.
$\eta_s^{(C)}$	Charging efficiency of BES system s .
$\eta_s^{(D)}$	Dicharging efficiency of BES system s .
Δt	Time-step duration.

E. Vectors and matrices

$\mathbf{m}$	Mean forecast vector.
ζ	Forecast error vector.
Σ	Covariance matrix of uncertainty vector.
$\mathbf{z}$	Decision vector of variables independent of uncertainties.
$\mathbf{w}(\zeta)$	Control vector of distributed resources.
$\mathbf{y}(\zeta)$	State vector of distributed resources and ADN.
$\bar{\mathbf{y}}$	Maximum permissible range of the state vector.
$\underline{\mathbf{y}}$	Minimum permissible range of the state vector.
$\bar{\lambda}$	Price vector.
$\bar{\zeta}$	Maximum of forecast error vector.
$\underline{\zeta}$	Minimum of forecast error vector.
$\Omega_{nt}^{(PF)}$	Equality constraints of power flow.
$\Gamma_{nt}^{(PF)}$	Inequality constraints of power flow.
$\mathbf{y}_{nt}^{(PF)}$	State vector of the grid.
$\Omega_s^{(BES)}$	Equality constraints of BES system s .
$\Gamma_s^{(BES)}$	Inequality constraints of BES system s .
$\mathbf{w}_s^{(BES)}$	Control vector of BES system s .
$\mathbf{y}_s^{(BES)}$	State variables vector of BES system s .
$\Gamma_i^{(PV)}$	Inequality constraints of PV system i .
$\mathbf{w}_i^{(PV)}$	Control vector of PV system i .

APPENDIX B

DETAILS OF POWER FLOW EQUATIONS AND SECURITY CONSTRAINTS

For all buses $n \in \mathcal{N}$ and time-steps $t \in \mathcal{T}$ of a given radial ADN, the detailed power flow equations $\Omega_{nt}^{(PF)}(\mathbf{y}_{nt}^{(PF)}(\zeta))$ and security constraints $\Gamma_{nt}^{(PF)}(\mathbf{y}_{nt}^{(PF)}(\zeta))$ are presented in the following. It is worth mentioning that all variables must be function of the uncertainty vector ζ that is dropped here for the sake of brevity.

$$p_{nt}^{(up)} = r_n l_{nt} - p_{nt}^{(net)} + \sum_{n' \in \mathcal{N}} u_{nn'} p_{n't}^{(up)}, \quad (26)$$

$$q_{nt}^{(up)} = x_n l_{nt} - q_{nt}^{(net)} + \sum_{n' \in \mathcal{N}} u_{nn'} q_{n't}^{(up)} - (v_{nt} + v_{nt}^{(up)}) b_n, \quad (27)$$

$$v_{nt}^{(up)} = v_{nt} + 2(r_n p_{nt}^{(up)} + x_n (q_{nt}^{(up)} + v_{nt}^{(up)} b_n)) - (r_n^2 + x_n^2) l_{nt}, \quad (28)$$

$$l_{nt} v_{nt}^{(up)} \geq (p_{nt}^{(up)})^2 + (q_{nt}^{(up)})^2, \quad (29)$$

$$\hat{p}_{nt}^{(up)} = -p_{nt}^{(net)} + \sum_{n' \in \mathcal{N}} u_{nn'} \hat{p}_{n't}^{(up)}, \quad (30)$$

$$\hat{q}_{nt}^{(up)} = -q_{nt}^{(net)} + \sum_{n' \in \mathcal{N}} u_{nn'} \hat{q}_{n't}^{(up)} - (\bar{v}_{nt}^{(up)} + \bar{v}_{nt}) b_n, \quad (31)$$

$$\bar{v}_{nt}^{(up)} = \bar{v}_{nt} + 2(r_n \hat{p}_{nt}^{(up)} + x_n (\hat{q}_{nt}^{(up)} + \bar{v}_{nt}^{(up)} b_n)), \quad (32)$$

$$\bar{p}_{nt}^{(up)} = r_n \bar{l}_{nt} - p_{nt}^{(net)} + \sum_{n' \in \mathcal{N}} u_{nn'} \bar{p}_{n't}^{(up)}, \quad (33)$$

$$\bar{q}_{nt}^{(up)} = x_n \bar{l}_{nt} - q_{nt}^{(net)} + \sum_{n' \in \mathcal{N}} u_{nn'} \bar{q}_{n't}^{(up)} - (v_{nt} + v_{nt}^{(up)}) b_n, \quad (34)$$

$$\bar{l}_{nt} v_{nt} \geq \max\{\hat{p}_{nt}^2, \bar{p}_{nt}^2\} + \max\{(\hat{q}_{nt} - \bar{v}_{nt} b_n)^2, (\bar{q}_{nt} - v_{nt} b_n)^2\}, \quad (35)$$

$$\bar{l}_{nt} v_{nt}^{(up)} \geq \max\{(\hat{p}_{nt}^{(up)})^2, (\bar{p}_{nt}^{(up)})^2\} + \max\{(\hat{q}_{nt}^{(up)} + \bar{v}_{nt}^{(up)} b_n)^2, (\bar{q}_{nt}^{(up)} + v_{nt}^{(up)} b_n)^2\}, \quad (36)$$

$$\bar{p}_{nt} = -p_{nt}^{(net)} + \sum_{n' \in \mathcal{N}} u_{nn'} \bar{p}_{n't}, \quad (37)$$

$$\bar{q}_{nt} = -q_{nt}^{(net)} + \sum_{n' \in \mathcal{N}} u_{nn'} \bar{q}_{n't}, \quad (38)$$

$$\hat{p}_{nt} = -p_{nt}^{(net)} + \sum_{n' \in \mathcal{N}} u_{nn'} \hat{p}_{n't}, \quad (39)$$

$$\hat{q}_{nt} = -q_{nt}^{(net)} + \sum_{n' \in \mathcal{N}} u_{nn'} \hat{q}_{n't}, \quad (40)$$

$$l_n^{(max)} v_{nt} \geq \max\{\hat{p}_{nt}, \bar{p}_{nt}\}^2 + \max\{\hat{q}_{nt}, \bar{q}_{nt}\}^2, \quad (41)$$

$$l_n^{(max)} v_{nt}^{(up)} \geq \max\{\hat{p}_{nt}^{(up)}, \bar{p}_{nt}^{(up)}\}^2 + \max\{\hat{q}_{nt}^{(up)}, \bar{q}_{nt}^{(up)}\}^2, \quad (42)$$

$$v_n^{(min)} \leq |v_{nt}| \leq v_n^{(max)}, \quad (43)$$

where parameter $l_n^{(max)}$ is the maximum permissible value of current square for line n ; parameters $v_n^{(min)}$ and $v_n^{(max)}$ are the minimum and maximum permissible magnitudes of voltage square at bus n . Here, $\mathbf{y}_{nt}^{(PF)}(\zeta)$ also includes the auxiliary variables $\hat{p}_{nt}^{(up)}(\zeta)$, $\hat{q}_{nt}^{(up)}(\zeta)$, $\bar{p}_{nt}^{(up)}(\zeta)$, $\bar{q}_{nt}^{(up)}(\zeta)$, $\hat{p}_{nt}(\zeta)$, $\hat{q}_{nt}(\zeta)$, $\bar{p}_{nt}(\zeta)$, $\bar{q}_{nt}(\zeta)$, $\bar{v}_{nt}(\zeta)$, $\bar{v}_{nt}^{(up)}(\zeta)$, and $\bar{l}_{nt}(\zeta)$;

APPENDIX C

DETAILS OF PV SYSTEMS CONSTRAINTS

In the following, the detailed inequality constraints $\Gamma_{it}^{(PV)}(\mathbf{w}_{it}^{(PV)}(\zeta))$ of a PV system $i \in \mathcal{I}_n$ at time-step $t \in \mathcal{T}$ are given. As proven in [20], the converter voltage limitation of a PV system is shown with a circle of the centre in $-3(v_i^{(grid,PV)})^2/x_i^{(PV)}$ in the Q-axis and the radius of $3v_i^{(grid,PV)}v_i^{(conv,PV)}/x_i^{(PV)}$.

$$(p_{it}^{(PV)})^2 + \left(q_{it}^{(PV)} + \frac{3(v_i^{(grid,PV)})^2}{x_i^{(PV)}}\right)^2 \leq \left(\frac{3v_i^{(grid,PV)}v_i^{(conv,PV)}}{x_i^{(PV)}}\right)^2, \quad (44)$$

where $v_i^{(grid,PV)}$, $v_i^{(conv,PV)}$, and $x_i^{(PV)}$ are the grid's voltage, converter voltage, and Thevenin reactance from the viewpoint of the PV system, respectively.

The converter current limitation of a PV system $i \in \mathcal{I}_n$ at time-step $t \in \mathcal{T}$ is a circle with the radius of $S_i^{(PV,max)}$ as,

$$(p_{it}^{(PV)})^2 + (q_{it}^{(PV)})^2 \leq (S_i^{(PV,max)})^2. \quad (45)$$

Finally, the available solar irradiance and positive generation limitations of a PV system $i \in \mathcal{I}_n$ at time-step $t \in \mathcal{T}$ are given in the following.

$$0 \leq p_{it}^{(PV)} \leq p_{it}^{(PV,max)}. \quad (46)$$

APPENDIX D

DETAILS OF BES SYSTEMS CONSTRAINTS

For each BES $s \in \mathcal{S}_n$, the detailed equality constraints $\Omega_s^{(BES)}(\mathbf{w}_s^{(BES)}(\zeta), \mathbf{y}_s^{(BES)}(\zeta))$ and inequality constraints $\Gamma_s^{(BES)}(\mathbf{w}_s^{(BES)}(\zeta), \mathbf{y}_s^{(BES)}(\zeta))$ are presented in the following. It is worth mentioning that all variables must be function of the uncertainty vector ζ that is dropped here for the sake of brevity.

$$e_{s(t+1)} = e_{st} + \left(\frac{p_{st}^{(BS,D)} \Delta t}{\eta_s^{(D)}} + \eta_s^{(C)} p_{st}^{(BS,C)} \Delta t \right) : \forall t \in \mathcal{T} - \{T\}, \quad (47)$$

$$0 \leq p_{st}^{(BS,C)} : \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (48)$$

$$0 \geq p_{st}^{(BS,D)} : \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (49)$$

$$p_{st}^{(BES)} = p_{st}^{(BS,C)} + p_{st}^{(BS,D)} : \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (50)$$

$$(p_{st}^{(BES)})^2 + (q_{st}^{(BES)})^2 \leq (S_s^{(BS,max)})^2 : \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (51)$$

$$e_s^{(min)} \leq e_{st} \leq e_s^{(max)} : \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (52)$$

$$\tilde{e}_{s(t+1)} = \tilde{e}_{st} + (p_{st}^{(BS,D)} \Delta t + p_{st}^{(BS,C)} \Delta t) : \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} - \{T\}, \quad (53)$$

$$e_s^{(min)} \leq \tilde{e}_{st} \leq e_s^{(max)} : \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (54)$$

where $\mathbf{y}_s^{(BES)}(\zeta) = \left[(p_{st}^{(BS,D)}(\zeta), p_{st}^{(BS,C)}(\zeta) : t \in \mathcal{T}), (\tilde{e}_{st}(\zeta) : t \in \mathcal{T}), (e_{st}(\zeta) : t \in \mathcal{T}) \right]$ is the vector of state variables; parameters $e_s^{(min)}$ and $e_s^{(max)}$ are the minimum and maximum permissible ranges of SoC; parameter $S_s^{(BS,max)}$ is the maximum apparent power flowing from the converter of BES system $s \in \mathcal{S}_n$.

APPENDIX E

PARAMETERS OF CASE STUDY

The parameters of the presented case study is given in Table I.

TABLE I: Parameters of the ADN.

Parameter	Value
Δt	10 min
$[r_n]$	[0.0146, 0.263, 0.20, 0.096, 0.028, 0.018]
$[x_n]$	[0.0383, 0.078, 0.009, 0.072, 0.009, 0.005]
$[2b_n]$	[0.0000, 0.229, 0.0312, 0.241, 0.091, 0.015]
$[S_i^{(PV,max)}]$	[200, 10, 60]
$[e_s^{(min)}]$	[0, 0]
$[e_s^{(max)}]$	[40, 160]
$[\eta_s^{(C)}]$	[0.95, 0.95]
$[\eta_s^{(D)}]$	[0.95, 0.95]
δ	10^{-3}

APPENDIX F

DISPATCH PLAN BASED ON STOCHASTIC PROGRAMMING

By clustering the samples of historical data, we obtain a set of scenarios $\mathcal{K} = \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$. Then, the optimization problem for obtaining dispatch plan of the ADN's operator based on stochastic programming is as follows.

$$\max_{\Xi^{(ST)}} \text{objective} = (2) \quad (55)$$

Subject to:

$$p_{ntk}^{(net)} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_n} p_{itk}^{(PV)} + \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}_n} p_{stk}^{(BES)} - p_{ntk}^{(DM)} : \forall n, t, k, \quad (56)$$

$$q_{ntk}^{(net)} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_n} q_{itk}^{(PV)} + \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}_n} q_{stk}^{(BES)} - q_{ntk}^{(DM)} : \forall n, t, k, \quad (57)$$

$$p_{ntk}^{(up)} = r_n l_{ntk} - p_{ntk}^{(net)} + \sum_{n' \in \mathcal{N}} u_{nn'} p_{n't}^{(up)} : \forall n, t, k, \quad (58)$$

$$q_{ntk}^{(up)} = x_n l_{ntk} - q_{ntk}^{(net)} + \sum_{n' \in \mathcal{N}} u_{nn'} q_{n't}^{(up)} - (v_{ntk} + v_{ntk}^{(up)}) b_n : \quad (59)$$

$$v_{ntk}^{(up)} = v_{ntk} + 2 \left(r_n p_{ntk}^{(up)} + x_n (q_{ntk}^{(up)} + v_{ntk}^{(up)} b_n) \right) - (r_n^2 + x_n^2) l_{ntk} : \quad (60)$$

$$l_{ntk} v_{ntk}^{(up)} \geq \left(p_{ntk}^{(up)} \right)^2 + \left(q_{ntk}^{(up)} \right)^2 : \forall n, t, k, \quad (61)$$

$$\hat{p}_{ntk}^{(up)} = -p_{ntk}^{(net)} + \sum_{n' \in \mathcal{N}} u_{nn'} \hat{p}_{n't}^{(up)} : \forall n, t, k, \quad (62)$$

$$\hat{q}_{ntk}^{(up)} = -q_{ntk}^{(net)} + \sum_{n' \in \mathcal{N}} u_{nn'} \hat{q}_{n't}^{(up)} - (\bar{v}_{ntk}^{(up)} + \bar{v}_{ntk}) b_n : \forall n, t, k, \quad (63)$$

$$\bar{v}_{ntk}^{(up)} = \bar{v}_{ntk} + 2 \left(r_n \hat{p}_{ntk}^{(up)} + x_n (\hat{q}_{ntk}^{(up)} + \bar{v}_{ntk}^{(up)} b_n) \right) : \forall n, t, k, \quad (64)$$

$$\bar{p}_{ntk}^{(up)} = r_n \bar{l}_{ntk} - p_{ntk}^{(net)} + \sum_{n' \in \mathcal{N}} u_{nn'} \bar{p}_{n't}^{(up)} : \forall n, t, k, \quad (65)$$

$$\bar{q}_{ntk}^{(up)} = x_n \bar{l}_{ntk} - q_{ntk}^{(net)} + \sum_{n' \in \mathcal{N}} u_{nn'} \bar{q}_{n't}^{(up)} - (v_{ntk} + v_{ntk}^{(up)}) b_n : \quad (66)$$

$$\bar{l}_{ntk} v_{ntk} \geq \max\{\hat{p}_{ntk}^2, \bar{p}_{ntk}^2\} + \max\{(\hat{q}_{ntk} - \bar{v}_{ntk} b_n)^2, (\bar{q}_{ntk} - v_{ntk} b_n)^2\} : \forall n, t, k, \quad (67)$$

$$\bar{l}_{ntk} v_{ntk}^{(up)} \geq \max\{(\hat{p}_{ntk}^{(up)})^2, (\bar{p}_{ntk}^{(up)})^2\} + \max\{(\hat{q}_{ntk}^{(up)} + \bar{v}_{ntk}^{(up)} b_n)^2, (\bar{q}_{ntk}^{(up)} + v_{ntk}^{(up)} b_n)^2\} : \forall n, t, k, \quad (68)$$

$$\bar{p}_{ntk} = -p_{ntk}^{(net)} + \sum_{n' \in \mathcal{N}} u_{nn'} \bar{p}_{n't}^{(up)} : \forall n, t, k, \quad (69)$$

$$\bar{q}_{ntk} = -q_{ntk}^{(net)} + \sum_{n' \in \mathcal{N}} u_{nn'} \bar{q}_{n't}^{(up)} : \forall n, t, k, \quad (70)$$

$$\hat{p}_{ntk} = -p_{ntk}^{(net)} + \sum_{n' \in \mathcal{N}} u_{nn'} \hat{p}_{n't}^{(up)} : \forall n, t, k, \quad (71)$$

$$\hat{q}_{ntk} = -q_{ntk}^{(net)} + \sum_{n' \in \mathcal{N}} u_{nn'} \hat{q}_{n't}^{(up)} : \forall n, t, k, \quad (72)$$

$$l_n^{(max)} v_{ntk} \geq \max\{\hat{p}_{ntk}, \bar{p}_{ntk}\}^2 + \max\{\hat{q}_{ntk}, \bar{q}_{ntk}\}^2 : \forall n, t, k, \quad (73)$$

$$l_n^{(max)} v_{ntk}^{(up)} \geq \max\{\hat{p}_{ntk}^{(up)}, \bar{p}_{ntk}^{(up)}\}^2 + \max\{\hat{q}_{ntk}^{(up)}, \bar{q}_{ntk}^{(up)}\}^2 : \forall n, t, k, \quad (74)$$

$$v_n^{(min)} \leq |v_{ntk}| \leq v_n^{(max)} : \forall n, t, k, \quad (75)$$

$$e_{s(t+1)k} = e_{stk} + \left(\frac{p_{stk}^{(BS,D)} \Delta t}{\eta_s^{(D)}} + \eta_s^{(C)} p_{stk}^{(BS,C)} \Delta t \right) : \forall s, t, k, \quad (76)$$

$$0 \leq p_{stk}^{(BS,C)} : \forall s, t, k, \quad (77)$$

$$0 \geq p_{stk}^{(BS,D)} : \forall s, t, k, \quad (78)$$

$$p_{stk}^{(BES)} = p_{stk}^{(BS,C)} + p_{stk}^{(BS,D)} : \forall s, t, k, \quad (79)$$

$$(p_{stk}^{(BES)})^2 + (q_{stk}^{(BES)})^2 \leq (S_s^{(BS,max)})^2 : \forall s, t, k, \quad (80)$$

$$e_s^{(min)} \leq e_{stk} \leq e_s^{(max)} : \forall s, t, k, \quad (81)$$

$$\tilde{e}_{s(t+1)k} = \tilde{e}_{stk} + \left(p_{stk}^{(BS,D)} \Delta t + p_{stk}^{(BS,C)} \Delta t \right) : \forall s, t, k, \quad (82)$$

$$e_s^{(min)} \leq \tilde{e}_{stk} \leq e_s^{(max)} : \forall s, t, k, \quad (83)$$

$$\left(p_{itk}^{(PV)} \right)^2 + \left(q_{itk}^{(PV)} + \frac{3(v_i^{(grid,PV)})^2}{x_i^{(PV)}} \right)^2 \leq \left(\frac{3v_i^{(grid,PV)} v_i^{(conv,PV)}}{x_i^{(PV)}} \right)^2 : \quad (84)$$

$$\left(p_{itk}^{(PV)} \right)^2 + \left(q_{itk}^{(PV)} \right)^2 \leq (S_i^{(PV,max)})^2 : \forall i, t, k, \quad (85)$$

$$0 \leq p_{itk}^{(PV)} \leq p_{itk}^{(PV,max)} : \forall i, t, k, \quad (86)$$

$$|p_t^{(SC)} + p_{itk}^{(DP)} - p_{0tk}| \leq \delta : \forall t, k, \quad (87)$$

$$|q_t^{(SC)} + q_{itk}^{(DP)} - q_{0tk}| \leq \delta : \forall t, k, \quad (88)$$

where the proposed problem is second-order cone programming.